

TABLE 6—COMPETITIVE FACTORS INVOLVED IN REPLACEMENT OF LIGAND A₂ BY A₁

A ₂	A ₁	ΔF _{2,000} cals/mole	ΔH _{2,000} cals/mole	ΔS _{2,000} cals/mole/degree
NH ₃	CH ₃ NH ₂	+350	-2850	-10.70
NH ₃	C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂	+300	-3850	-12.85
NH ₃	C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	+40	-9550	-25.60
CH ₃ NH ₂	C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂	-300	-980	-2.00
CH ₃ NH ₂	C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	-210	-6700	-14.90
C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂	C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	-10	-5700	+12.75

VO₂²⁺ will have a square pyramidal configuration. It is expected that this will assume either a regular or distorted octahedron structure when the ammonia or amine molecules are added to it. Search of literature¹¹⁻¹³ reveals a distorted octahedron structure for a vanadyl ion. With ammonia adduct, free energy changes seem to be maximum and decreases somewhat when the length of carbon chain in the amine added increases. The entropy effects are in reverse order. The order of the entropy units for butyl amine adduct predicts that a spontaneous replacement in this case is rather difficult. There are approximations involved in assuming a regular octahedron structure for VO₂²⁺ complex. In fact, crystal field theory predicts that the change from a regular octahedron to the square pyramidal structure is associated with an increased stability. The data presented in Table 6 merely shows that variations in symmetry of the complex molecule may take place and a preferred configuration will be assumed by the complex molecule when the ligand A gets attached to it loosely.

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Extraction and Complexometric Determination of Copper in Brass using Dimethyl Glyoxime as an Indicator

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DIMETHYL Glyoxime¹ has already been used as an indicator for the complexometric titration of copper by the present author. The use of dimethyl glyoxime in analytical chemistry is well known. It has been used for the determination² of Ni, Pd(II), Pt(II), Iron(II) and Bismuth.

This paper reports the use of dimethyl glyoxime as an indicator for the complexometric titration of copper in brass or bronze samples.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions :

- (i) EDTA solution : a stock solution of 0.1M EDTA was prepared by dissolving 37.23 gm of EDTA (Sodium salt) in 1 litre of distilled water.
- (ii) Dimethyl Glyoxime (2%) : Prepared by dissolving in absolute alcohol.
- (iii) EDTA solution (4%) : Prepared in distilled water.
- (iv) Sodium diethyl dithio carbamates (1%) : The solution is prepared in distilled water.
- (v) Ammonium Hydroxide : Dilute (2%)
- (vi) Tartaric Acid : Solid
- (vii) Ethyl acetate : B.D.H/E. MERCK
- (viii) Silver nitrate solution : 2% in distilled water.

Procedure : 0.5 gm drillings of the brass or bronze sample is dissolved in dilute nitric acid (1 : 2) and tartaric acid (about 0.2 gm) in a beaker and transferred in a 250 ml volumetric flask and the solution is diluted upto the mark. 250 ml of the solution is drawn in a separating funnel. 15 ml of EDTA solution (4%) is added to it, the pH is maintained at 8.5 with ammonium hydroxide. Now

copper is precipitated with 50 ml of sodium diethyl dithio carbamate³ solution (1%) and the ppt. is extracted with ethyl acetate. All copper is removed in one extraction. The ethyl acetate layer is washed and copper from the organic phase is displaced (15 ml) with silver nitrate⁴ solution. Finally, the solution is strongly diluted and made weakly basic with ammonium hydroxide and then the copper is titrated with EDTA using 10 ml of dimethyl glyoxime (1%) as an indicator from red to blue end point.

Results and Discussion

A number of brass and bronze samples are tested by this method against the electrolysis method and iodometric method and their results are indicated in Table I, which are in good agreement with one another.

TABLE I

Particulars of Samples	Iodometric Method	Cu by Electrolysis	Cu by New Method*
No. 1	70.02	70.04	70.11
No. 2	70.18	70.25	70.20
No. 3	68.48	68.56	68.50
No. 4	70.52	70.58	70.62
No. 5	67.70	67.77	67.74

* Average of 3 results.

Determination of copper by electrolysis though accurate is expensive and time consuming. On the other hand, the new method is cheaper, takes much less time and the results are reproducible as well.

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Analytical Applications of 5-Hydroxy-1,4-Naphthoquinone (Juglone)

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THE present note extends the application of juglone as a pH indicator¹ in the determination of glycine and hippuric acid, and deals with its use as a metal ion indicator in the estimation of nickel ion in solution complexometrically with hippuric acid as a titrant at 6.8 pH.

In the titration of hippuric acid (N/50 and N/100) with NaOH (N/46.30 and N/96), juglone with pH range 7.8-9.9 and colour change: yellow to violet, was found more suitable than phenolphthalein, methyl-red and lapachol². Standard deviation as low as 0.05 could be achieved in the case of juglone. Relative errors in different case are:

Indicator	Relative Error (%)	
	Analyte : N/50	Titrant : N/100 N/46.30 N/96
Juglone	0.21	0.41
Phenolphthalein	0.75	2.50
Methyl-red	3.45	4.58
Lapachol	2.15	5.41

In the estimation of glycine, juglone as a pH indicator in the place of phenolphthalein, employing sorenson formula in titration method, with relative error as 0.02% is quantitative in nature. Standard deviation as low as 0.02 could be achieved.

Juglone as Metal Ion Indicator :

Nickel-juglone complex with metal ligand molar ratio of 1 : 2 is less stable than nickel-hippuric acid complex having metal to ligand combining ratio as 1 : 2. With progressive complexation of nickel ion by hippuric acid at 6.8 pH, nickel ion is ultimately displaced from nickel-juglone complex (red) to leave free juglone (yellow). Juglone exhibits acid-base behaviour in the pH range 7.8-9.9 in which it exhibits violet colour. It is yellow below 7.8 pH. Nickel forms red complex³ with juglone at 6.8 pH.

Under the experimental conditions, juglone as a metal ion indicator with relative error as 0.6% appears to be suitable in the estimation of nickel ion complexometrically. E.D.T.A. titration yielded far better results. Standard deviation as low as 0.3 could be achieved. Ions like Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺, Al³⁺, Fe³⁺, interfered.